

ANNOTATED BIBLIOGRAPHY

PRIMARY SOURCES

Dictionaries and Encyclopaediae

Graves, Algernon. *The Royal Academy of Arts: A Complete Dictionary of Contributors and Their Work from Its Foundation in 1769 to 1904*. London: Henry Graves and Co., Ltd., and George Bell and Sons, 1905. Reprint, London: Kingsmead Reprints and Hilmarton Manor Press, 1989.

Authoritative reference work that includes a complete listing of all artists, famous and obscure, who exhibited at the Royal Academy from its beginning until the early years of the twentieth century. This work is cited by all subsequent authors writing about artists whose works were exhibited there within this date range. The entry for each artist includes dates works were exhibited, titles of works, exhibition numbers assigned to works, and artists' addresses at the time works were exhibited. An invaluable research tool for finding exhibition reviews and articles.

Smith, William, ed. *A Dictionary of Greek and Roman Biography and Mythology*. London: John Murray, 1876. A complete, multi-volume reference work containing detailed entries on every ancient historical and mythological personage which may very well have been used by late Victorian artists. Because the information contained therein is drawn primarily from ancient literary sources (cited within the text) rather than dependant upon archaeological evidence, it remains authoritative after 130 years. This book will be useful in my research as a fact-checking tool, but also to ensure that my understanding of an ancient character comes from a source contemporaneous to the late Victorians.

General Literature

Hope, Thomas. *Costume of the Ancients*. New York: Henry G. Bohn, 1841. Revised ed. Multi-volume work of ink drawings depicting classical dress, hairstyles, and archaeological objects such as pottery, metalwork, and furniture. Illustrations are drawn from actual objects; i.e., costumes and hairstyles have been observed from ancient statues. Hope is known for his archaeological accuracy, and so it seems likely that artists working in London during the second half of the nineteenth century would have been aware of these works and may well have used them as sources. One particular drawing of a table featuring lion monopodia is strikingly similar in design to those seen in several paintings by Godward and Bulleid. I would like to use this work in my analysis of Godward's costume in comparison to other Victorian classicists in my discussion of archaeological truth.

Jameson, Anna. *Legends of the Madonna as Presented in the Fine Arts: Forming the Third Series of Sacred and Legendary Art*. London: Longman, Brown, Green, and Longmans, 1852. Jameson, Anna. *Sacred and Legendary Art Vols. I and II: Containing Legends of the Angels and Archangels, the Evangelists, the Apostles, the Doctors of the Church, and St. Mary Magdalene*. London: Longman, Brown, Green, Longmans, and Roberts, 1848. 3d ed., 1857. Jameson, Anna. *Memoirs of the Early Italian Painters, and of the Progress of Painting in Italy. Cimabue to Bassano: A New Edition, with Portraits*. London: John Murray, 1868. These three works by Anna Jameson were the authoritative sources for late Victorian British art students seeking to understand the Catholic art of the Renaissance. Along with Jameson's historical analyses and descriptions, the stories and illustrations contained therein exerted a strong influence upon the Pre-Raphaelite painters, most especially Rossetti. Jameson's books may have also influenced classicist painters such as Godward, and I plan to use them to look for clues.

Periodical Literature

Barrington, E. I. 'Is a Great School of Art Possible in the Present Day?' *The Nineteenth Century*, (April 1879): 714–32. Calvin, Sidney. 'On the Study of Classical Art.' *The Fortnightly Review*, (November 1878): 661–81. 'The State of Art in England.' *Blackwood's Magazine*, (May 1882): 609–22. These three articles from nineteenth-century periodicals contain opinions that exemplify contemporary attitudes toward the art and artists of the time. Along with exhibition reviews, these writings will help to flesh out a picture of the environment in which the works of Godward and other artists were created.

Prints, Drawings, and Archives

Eighty Four Etched Fac-Similes on a Reduced Scale, After the Original Sketches by M. Angelo and Raffaele in the University Galleries, Oxford. Second series. Etched and published by Joseph Fisher. Oxford, UK: Messrs. Parker, 1862. A book of well-executed etchings after a variety of drawings by Michelangelo and Raphael. In the production of this book and another similar work, Fisher rendered their designs accessible to any artist working in late Victorian London by way of the British Museum. In exploring sources for the works of the late Victorian classicists, this book contains several interesting possibilities to use for comparison. Unfortunately, reproductions of the etchings are prohibitively expensive, and it is doubtful whether it will be economically feasible for me to use any of Fisher's plates as illustrations in my dissertation.

SECONDARY SOURCES

Dictionaries and Encyclopaediae

Greutzner, A., and Jane Johnson. *The Dictionary of British Artists 1880–1940*. Woodbridge, Suffolk, UK: Antique Collectors' Club, 1988. Reprint. Vincent, Adrian. *A Companion to Victorian and Edwardian Artists*. Hong Kong: Wing King Tong Co, Ltd., 1991. Waters, Grant M. *Dictionary of British Artists Working 1900–50*. Eastbourne, UK: Eastbourne Fine Art, 1975. Wood, Christopher. *Dictionary of British Art Volume IV: Victorian Painters*. Woodbridge, Suffolk, UK: Antique Collectors' Club, 1995. All of these works contain basic biographical information for the artists who are relevant to my research. The volume by Christopher Wood is the most authoritative, cited by virtually every other author writing about painters of the period. Collectively, these sources will be useful in the introductory portions of my writing.

Monnington, T. *Royal Academy Exhibitors 1905–1970: A Dictionary of Artists and Their Work in the Royal Academy of Arts*. East Ardsley, Wakefield, Yorkshire, UK: EP Publishing Ltd., 1981. A work similar to the 1905 publication of Algernon Graves but covering a later period. It contains the same kind of detailed information about the artist and their work as contained in the original, and since Godward and his peers exhibited into the early decades of the twentieth century, it will be helpful in finding articles and exhibition reviews for the period after 1905.

Picken, Mary Brooks. *The Fashion Dictionary: Fabric, Sewing, and Dress as Expressed in 'The Language of Fashion'*. Edited by Claire Valentine. New York: Funk and Wagnalls Co., 1957. A well-organised, generously-illustrated reference work covering the full range of fashion from ancient to modern times. This book has already been helpful in defining somewhat obscure and potentially confusing components of ancient costume, which I will address in my discussion of archaeological accuracy. I may balance this older book with a more up-to-date reference work to monitor the possibility of changes in meaning over time, which may account for an apparent confusion of terms in Vern Swanson's monograph on Godward.

Monographs

- Becker, Edwin, Edward Morris, Elizabeth Prettejohn, and Julian Treuherz, eds. *Sir Lawrence Alma-Tadema*. Liverpool, UK: Walker Art Gallery, 1997. Lippincott, Louise. *Lawrence Alma Tadema: Spring*. Malibu, CA: The J. Paul Getty Museum, 1991. Tomlinson, Richard. *The Athens of Alma Tadema*. Phoenix Mill, Gloucester, UK: Alan Sutton Publishing, Ltd., 1991. The analysis of Alma-Tadema's painting *Spring* by Lippincott is cited by several other authors including Prettejohn in her article 'Lawrence Alma-Tadema and the Modern City of Ancient Rome.' Both Lippincott's book and the monograph by Becker, Morris, Prettejohn, and Treuherz will be useful in my discussion of the function of the ancient environment in the classicist paintings of Alma-Tadema, Poynter, Godward, Bulleid, and Ryland. Tomlinson's book focuses primarily on Alma-Tadema's photo archive and will probably be of little in my research.
- Jones, Stephen, Christopher Newall, Leonée Ormond, et. al. Edited by Phyllis Freeman. *Frederic, Lord Leighton: Eminent Victorian Artist*. New York: Harry N. Abrams, Inc. with Royal Academy of Arts, London, 1997. Newall, Christopher. *The Art of Lord Leighton*. Oxford, UK: Phaidon Press, Ltd., 1990. Mannings, David. *Sir Joshua Reynolds: A Complete Catalogue of His Paintings*. Catalogued by Martin Postle. New Haven, CT, and London: Yale University Press, 2000. Oberhuber, Konrad. *Raphael: The Paintings*. New York: Prestel Verlag 1999. Monographs of certain artists whose works I will be using for comparison only to play a minor role.
- Swanson, Vern Grosvenor. *John William Godward: The Eclipse of Classicism*. Woodbridge, Suffolk, UK: Antique Collectors' Club, 1998. The singular monograph and catalogue raisonné on Godward to which all other writers mentioning Godward's work refer. This will be the main source upon which my paper will depend for facts about Godward's life and for information about and images of his paintings.

General Literature

- Adams, Kimberly VanEsveld. *Our Lady of Victorian Feminism: The Madonna in the Work of Anna Jameson, Margaret Fuller, and George Eliot*. Athens, OH: Ohio University Press, 2001.
- Edwards, Catharine and Michael Liversidge, eds. *Imagining Rome: British Artists and Rome in the Nineteenth Century*. London: Merrell Holberton, 1996. Jenkins, Ian. *Archaeologists and Aesthetes in the Sculpture Galleries of the British Museum 1800–1939*. London: The British Museum Press, 1992. Pevsner, Nikolaus, ed. *The Pelican History of Art. The Art and Architecture of Ancient Egypt*, by W. Stephenson Smith. Harmondsworth, Middlesex, UK: Penguin Books, Ltd., 1958.
- Gaunt, William. *Victorian Olympus*. London: Jonathan Cape, Ltd., 1952. Revised ed., 1975. Lambourne, Lionel. *Victorian Painting*. London: Phaidon Press, Ltd., 1999. Maas, Jeremy. *Victorian Painters*. London: Barrie and Jenkins, Ltd., 1969. Reprint edition 1988. McConkey, Kenneth. *Edwardian Portraits: Images of an Age of Opulence*. Woodbridge, Suffolk, UK: Antique Collectors' Club, 1987. Morris, Edward. *French Art in Nineteenth-Century Britain*. London: Yale University Press, 2005. Reynolds, Graham. *Victorian Painting*. London: Studio Vista, Ltd., 1966. Treuherz, Julian. *Victorian Painting*. London: Thames and Hudson, Ltd., 1993. Warner, Malcom, Anne Helmreich, and Charles Brock. *The Victorians: British Painting 1837–1901*. New York: Harry N. Abrams, Inc., 1997. All of these publications focus on artistic periods rather than individual artists and so are useful for background information in an introduction. Both *Victorian Olympus* by Gaunt and *Victorian Painters* by Maas are the most authoritative, cited by every later publication about painting of the period.
- Houston, Mary G. *A Technical History of Costume Vol. II: Ancient Greek, Roman and Byzantine Costume*. London: Adams and Charles Black, 1931. 2d ed., 1947. Dated but thorough source for definitions of various parts of costume both ancient and modern loaded with illustrations which will be useful for the first half of my paper in an analysis of archaeological accuracy.

- Panofsky, Erwin. 'The Neoplatonic Movement and Michelangelo (1939).' In *Michelangelo: Selected Readings*, ed. William E. Wallace, 559–98. New York: Garland Publishing, Inc., 1999. A compilation of writings by authorities on Michelangelo. The particular section by Panofsky explains the relationship between Michelangelo's sculpture and Neoplatonic philosophy, and will be useful during the second part of my paper in which my focus will be the figure.
- Rueger, Christoph. *Musical Instruments and Their Decoration: Historical Gems of European Culture*. Cincinnati, OH: Seven Hills Books, 1986. This may not be the best reference for my purpose, but it is useful insofar as it briefly describes the ancient hierarchy of musical instruments, with percussion instruments traditionally more bestial and stringed instruments more angelic. This may be useful for reading paintings during the second part of my paper in which my focus will be the figure.
- Smith, Alison. *The Victorian Nude: Sexuality, Morality and Art*. Manchester, UK: Manchester University Press, 1996. This book gives the subject of the nude in Victorian art a thorough treatment, putting it into its social, political, and cultural context and should be helpful for the second part of my dissertation which will focus on the figure.
- Wood, Christopher. *Olympian Dreamers: Victorian Classical Painters 1860–1914*. London: Constable and Company, Ltd., 1983. The authoritative publication about Victorian classical-subject painters in Britain, but primarily of the generation before Godward. This will be a main source of information about these painters and should prove to be indispensable in my research.

Periodical Literature

- Barzman, Karen-Edis. 'Beyond the Canon: Feminism, Postmodernism, and the History of Art.' *The Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism* 52, No. 3 (Summer 1994): 327–39. Faxon, Alicia Craig. 'Review: Evelyn Pickering De Morgan and the Allegorical Body by Elise Lawton Smith.' *Woman's Art Journal* 24, No. 2 (Autumn 2003–Winter 2004): 48–9. Finch, Casey. "'Hooked and Buttoned Together: Victorian Underwear and Representations of the Female Body.'" *Victorian Studies* 34, No. 3 (Spring 1991): 337–63. Fraser, Hilary. 'Women and the Ends of Art History: Vision and Corporeality in Nineteenth-Century Critical Discourse.' *Victorian Studies* 42, No. 1 (Autumn 1998/1999): 77–100. Loss, Archie K. 'The Pre-Raphaelite Woman, the Symbolist 'Femme-Enfant,' and the Girl with Long Flowing Hair in the Earlier Work of Joyce.' *Journal of Modern Literature* 3, No. 1 (February 1973): 3–23. 'Review: *Exposed: The Victorian Nude* by Alison Smith.' *Woman's Art Journal* 24, No. 1 (Spring–Summer 2003): 55. Lawton Smith, Elise. 'The Art of Evelyn De Morgan.' *Woman's Art Journal* 18, No. 2 (August 1997–8): 3–10. Thomson, Jan. 'The Role of Women in the Iconography of Art Nouveau.' *Art Journal* 31, No. 2 (Winter 1971–2): 158–67. All of these articles deal with various aspects of nudity and/or representations of the female body in art during the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. Whilst I will probably not use all of these articles, the ones that remain will be useful during the second part of my paper in which I will focus on the figure.
- Bergström, Ingvar. 'Disguised Symbolism in 'Madonna' Pictures and Still Life: I.' *The Burlington Magazine* 97, No. 631 (October 1955): 303–8. Fiocco, Guiseppe. 'A Newly Discovered Tondo by Botticelli.' *The Burlington Magazine for Connoisseurs* 57, No. 331 (October 1930): 152–5. Goffen, Rona. 'Icon and Vision: Giovanni Bellini's Half-Length Madonnas.' *The Art Bulletin* 57, No. 4 (December 1975): 487–518. Goffen, Rona. 'Mary's Motherhood According to Leonardo and Michelangelo.' *Artibus et Historiae* 20, No. 40 (1999): 35–69. These articles discuss Marian art of the Renaissance and will be useful in my discussion of Godward's figures during the second part of my paper.

- Even, Yael. 'The Heroine as Hero in Michelangelo's Art.' *Woman's Art Journal* 11, No. 1 (Spring–Summer 1990): 29–33. Article discussing Michelangelo's tendency to masculinise women as in his art analysed as a psychological manifestation of his homoerotic desires. This could be an interesting contrast with Godward, whose art probably reflects a different sort of tendency and may be useful during the second part of my paper in which I will focus on the figure.
- Hall, H. R. 'Objects of Tut'ankhamūn in the British Museum.' *The Journal of Egyptian Archaeology* 14, No. ½ (June 1928): 74–7. This article will be used to check the archaeological accuracy of Poynter's *Israel Into Egypt*.
- Jenkins, Ian. 'Frederic Lord Leighton and Greek Vases.' *The Burlington Magazine* 125, No. 967 (October 1983): 596–603, 5. Prettejohn, Elizabeth. 'Lawrence Alma-Tadema and the Modern City of Ancient Rome.' *The Art Bulletin* 84, No. 1 (March 2002): 115–29. These articles discuss the accuracy of archaeological details in the paintings of Leighton and Alma-Tadema and will be vital to my analysis of Godward's paintings in relation to others during the first half of my paper.
- Harris, Wendell V. 'Ruskin's Theoretic Practicality and the Royal Academy's Aesthetic Idealism.' *Nineteenth-Century Literature* 52, No. 1 (June 1997): 80–102. Ludley, David A. 'Anna Jameson and D.G. Rossetti: His Use of Her Histories.' *Woman's Art Journal* 12, No. 2 (Autumn 1991–Winter 1992): 29–33. Stein, Richard L. 'The Pre-Raphaelite Tennyson.' *Victorian Studies* 24, No. 3 (Spring 1981): 278–301. These articles focus on the influence of Victorian writers on the painting of the period and will be useful possibly for the introduction and conclusion but most likely for the second half of my paper in which I discuss Godward's figures.
- Olson, Roberta J. M. 'Lost and Partially Found: The Tondo, a Significant Florentine Art Form, in Documents of the Renaissance.' *Artibus et Historiae* 14, No. 27 (1993): 31–65. Vermeule, III, Cornelius C. 'A Greek Theme and Its Survivals: The Ruler's Shield (Tondo Image) in Tomb and Temple.' *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society* 109, No. 6 (December 10, 1965): 361–97. Zimmer, William. 'The Tondo.' *Art Journal* 50, No. 1 (Spring 1991): 60–3. The two articles provide background information about the tondo, a circular format that was much favoured by Godward and which I plan to discuss toward the end of the dissertation in relation to the figure. Olson's article appears to have been incorporated into a book on the subject, which seems to be the only publication devoted exclusively to a discussion of this format and which I will probably defer to.

Exhibition Catalogues

- Alseson, Robyn, Tim Barringer, Susan P. Casteras, et. Al. *Pre-Raphaelite and Other Masters: The Andrew Lloyd Webber Collection*. London: Royal Academy of Arts in association with Christie's, 2003. Anderson, Gail-Nina and Joanne Wright. *Heaven on Earth: The Religion of Beauty in Late Victorian Art: The Catalogue of an Exhibition at the Djanogly Art Gallery, University of Nottingham Arts Centre*. London: University of Nottingham Arts Centre in association with Lund Humphries Publishers, Ltd., 1994. These two catalogues contain mostly Pre-Raphaelite works, but Anderson and Wright's *Heaven on Earth* discusses artistic influence which may have also touched artists such as Godward.
- Brighton College. *Life at Arm's Length: Sir Edward Poynter Bt, GCVO, PRA 1836 – 1919: A Pupil at Brighton College from 1849 – 1850: A Retrospective Exhibition*. Introductory essay and catalogue annotations by Julian Freeman. Brighton College 150th Anniversary Programme, Brighton College, London, 1995. An unpublished catalogue which I plan to use for background information on Poynter and his painting *Israel Into Egypt*.

Edwards, Catharine. 'The Roads to Rome.' In *Imagining Rome: British Artists and Rome in the Nineteenth Century*, eds. Catharine Edwards and Michael Liversidge, 8–19. London: Merrell Holberton, 1996. Prettejohn, Elizabeth. 'Catalogue II: Recreating Rome.' In *Imagining Rome: British Artists and Rome in the Nineteenth Century*, eds. Catharine Edwards and Michael Liversidge, 125–70. London: Merrell Holberton, 1996. Prettejohn, Elizabeth. 'Recreating Rome in Victorian Painting: From History to Genre.' In *Imagining Rome: British Artists and Rome in the Nineteenth Century*, eds. Catharine Edwards and Michael Liversidge, 54–69. London: Merrell Holberton, 1996. These four parts of the same catalogue discuss different facets of the Victorian fascination with depicting the ancient past and will be useful in my discussion of archaeological specificity.

Treble, Rosemary, ed. *Great Victorian Pictures: Their Paths to Fame: An Arts Council Exhibition 1978*. London: Lawrence and Company, Ltd., 1978. This catalogue will be useful for information about specific well-known works of art.

Gowing, Lawrence, Mary Anne Stevens, Helen Valentine, et. Al. Mary Anne Stevens, ed. *The Edwardians and After: The Royal Academy 1900–1950*. London: Royal Academy of Arts in association with Weidenfeld and Nicolson, Ltd., 1988. This book may be useful in a comparison of Godward's style to those of other early twentieth-century painters.

Prints, Drawings, and Archives

Gere, J.A., and Nicholas Turner. *Drawings by Raphael from the Royal Library, the Ashmolean, the British Museum, Chatsworth and other English Collections*. London: British Museum Publications, Ltd., 1983. Reprint, 1984. Oberhuber, Konrad, ed. *The Works of Marcantonio Raimondi and His School*, vols. 26 and 27, *The Illustrated Bartsch*. Edited by Walter L. Strauss. New York: Abaris Books, Inc., 1978. These publications contain images of drawings which may have inspired Godward and other Victorian painters contemporary with him and will be most useful in my exploration of the derivation of his figures.